

Active metallic indium mediated carbon-carbon bond formation in aqueous media : Barbier-type allylation of aldehydes

Hua-Yue Wu*, Jin-Chang Ding, Miao-Chang Liu and Jing Gao

Department of Chemistry, Wenzhou Normal College, Wenzhou 325027, P. R. China

E-mail : hywu3@163.com Fax : 86-577-88339081

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Mediated by active metallic indium generated *in situ* from Sm/InCl₃·4H₂O bimetallic system, aldehydes and allylic bromide undergo efficient Barbier-type allylation reaction to afford homoallylic alcohols in high yields under mild conditions in aqueous media.

Allylation of carbonyl compounds with allylmetals to give the corresponding homoallylic alcohols is considered to be one of the most important carbon-carbon bond formation methods in organic synthesis¹. Although a number of allylmetallic reagents so far have been developed to realize efficient allylation reaction of C=X electrophiles, most of them are air and moisture sensitive. Therefore, the allylation reaction is usually performed under strictly anhydrous condition in organic solvent. In recent years, there has been considerable interest in performing organometallic reactions in aqueous media². By using aqueous media, the inflammable and anhydrous organic solvent can be avoided. Moreover, compounds bearing reactive functional groups, such as hydroxyl and carboxylic, can be reacted directly without the protection-deprotection protocol in such reactions. Up to now, such aqueous organometallic-type reactions have been based on the Barbier-type conditions using various metals directly in aqueous media. Despite the success obtained, the use of metals, such as zinc and tin, directly in the Barbier-type allylation reactions in aqueous media often needs acid catalysts, heat or sonication reaction conditions, and in many cases leads to side reactions, such as reduction and/or Pinacol coupling of the carbonyl compound, Wurtz coupling of the halide.

Since the report of general approach for the preparation of highly reactive metal powders in 1972³, active metals have attracted considerable attention in organic synthesis⁴. Due to high reactivity of active metals, reactions are typically carried out more efficiently with higher chemo-selectivity, under milder conditions, and with a wider array of substrates than with other methods. While these results are interesting, a cardinal restriction in the use of active metals is the strict exclusion of moisture. It means that if active metals could be prepared in open air and the reactions mediated by

active metals could be realized in aqueous media, they would certainly be much more practical and useful in organic synthesis. As a continuation of our research interest aimed at greener chemistry, we have recently undertaken a program directed toward the application of active metallic indium generated *in situ* from metallic samarium and InCl₃·4H₂O in mediating organic reactions in aqueous media⁵. In the present communication, the allylation of aldehydes using active metallic indium is described which proceeds smoothly under very mild conditions in aqueous media to afford homoallylic alcohols in high yields as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

The reaction procedure for the allylation of aldehydes mediated by active metallic indium is very simple. In a typical experimental procedure indium(III) chloride suspended in THF-H₂O (8/1) mixture was treated with metallic samarium a kind of light black species (active metallic indium). Then, aldehyde (1) and allylic bromide (2) were added. An exothermic reaction occurred immediately. The mixture was stirred at room temperature. TLC results showed

that the reaction completed within several minutes and the desired homoallylic alcohol product was subsequently obtained with fairly good yields (Table 1).

Table 1. Preparation of homoallylic alcohols promoted by active metallic indium

Entry	Ar	Reaction time (min)	Product	Yield (%) ^a
1	C ₆ H ₅	5 (120 ^b)	3a	84 (0 ^b)
2	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	5	3b	83
3	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	5	3c	77
4	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	5	3d	87
5	3-BrC ₆ H ₄	5	3e	86
6	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	5	3f	92
7	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	5	3g	79
8	3-ClC ₆ H ₄	5	3h	82
9	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH	5	3i	78

^aIsolated yield of homoallylic alcohols. ^bIn the presence of Sm powder or indium trichloride alone.

As shown in Table 1, a number of substrates have been studied. The chloro, bromo and alkoxy groups of the substrates were tolerated under the reaction conditions. In addition, it should be noted that no reaction took place with either metallic samarium or indium trichloride alone (Table 1, entry 1). The reaction required no protection of inert atmosphere, thus make the whole process more convenient and practical. Compared to the use of zinc and tin where acid catalysts, heat or sonication were often required, allylation reactions with active metallic indium actually complete in several minutes without any promoters. In addition, when unsaturated aldehyde was used, no conjugation addition occurred and only 1,2-addition product was obtained (Table 1, entry 9).

Although the detailed mechanism of the above reaction has not been clarified yet, one possible mechanism for the allylation process may be that the active metallic indium reacts with the carbonyl compound by a single electron transfer process to give the radical anion intermediate. The ketyl radical anion couples with the allylic bromide to give the alkoxy radical, which on further reduction by the metal in another single electron transfer step gives the alkoxide anion, which is then protonated by water to the homoallylic alcohol product. Alternatively, one may also postulate that it is the allylic halide that reacts with the metal in a SET step to give the radical anion. The radical anion then couples with the carbonyl compound to give the alkoxy radical species, which on further reduction by the metal gives the product.

In conclusion, we have provided a new route to homoallylic alcohols, the advantages of which include high yields, simple and mild reaction conditions, and high chemoselectivity. Further studies to develop other new uses of InCl₃ and Sm bimetallic system are now in progress in our laboratory.

Experimental

¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AC 300 instrument. All samples were measured in CDCl₃ using TMS as internal standard. IR spectra were recorded on a Bruker-EQUINOX55 spectrometer. The reactions were performed in open air.

General procedure for the preparation of homoallylic alcohols:

In a 50 ml three-necked flask were placed InCl₃·4H₂O (1 mmol), metallic samarium (1 mmol), THF (4 ml), then to the mixture was slowly added H₂O (0.5 ml). Drastic reaction took place, and a kind of light black species appeared in 3 min which indicated that active metallic indium was readily prepared. Then a mixture of allylic bromide (1 mmol) and aldehydes (1 mmol) was added to the flask. After stirring for the time given in the Table 1, the mixture was quenched with diluted HCl (0.1 M, 2 ml) and extracted with ether (3 × 20 ml). The combined extract was washed with saturated brine (15 ml) and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. After evaporating the solvent under reduced pressure, the resulting crude product was purified by preparative TLC on silica gel using ethyl acetate-cyclohexane (1 : 8) as eluent. All the products were indentified.

3a, oil, ν_{\max} 3369, 3077, 2979, 1641 cm⁻¹, δ 2.50~2.55 (2H, m, -CH₂CH=CH₂), 3.23 (1H, br s, -OH), 4.72~4.77 (1H, m, ArCH), 5.13~5.20 (2H, m, -CH₂CH=CH₂), 5.75~5.86 (1H, m, -CH₂CH=CH₂), 7.29~7.38 (5H, m, ArH); **3b**, oil, ν_{\max} 3392, 3076, 2978, 1640 cm⁻¹, δ 2.36 (3H, s, -CH₃), 2.49~2.56 (2H, m, -CH₂CH=CH₂), 3.25 (1H, br s, -OH), 4.70~4.74 (1H, m, ArCH), 5.13~5.20 (2H, m, -CH₂CH=CH₂), 5.75~5.89 (1H, m, -CH₂CH=CH₂), 7.17 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, ArH), 7.26 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, ArH); **3c**, oil, ν_{\max} 3369, 3077, 2979, 1640 cm⁻¹, δ 2.47~2.51 (2H, m, -CH₂CH=CH₂), 3.12 (1H, br s, -OH), 3.80 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 4.65~4.70 (1H, m, ArCH), 5.09~5.16 (2H, m, -CH₂CH=CH₂), 5.73~5.82 (1H, m, -CH₂CH=CH₂), 6.88 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, ArH), 7.26 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, ArH); **3d**, oil, ν_{\max} 3391, 3078, 2979, 1641 cm⁻¹, δ 2.41~2.50 (2H, m, -CH₂CH=CH₂), 3.31 (1H, br s, -OH), 4.68~4.72 (1H, m, ArCH), 5.13~5.19 (2H, m, -CH₂CH=CH₂), 5.71~5.82 (1H, m, -CH₂CH=CH₂), 7.23 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, ArH), 7.47

(2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, ArH); **3e**, oil, ν_{\max} 3390, 3076, 2979, 1641 cm^{-1} , δ 2.45~2.53 (2H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 3.22 (1H, br s, -OH), 4.70~4.74 (1H, m, ArCH), 5.16~5.22 (2H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 5.75~5.85 (1H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 7.20~7.43 (3H, m, ArH), 7.54 (1H, s, ArH); **3f**, oil, ν_{\max} 3392, 3078, 2980, 1641 cm^{-1} , δ 2.40~2.46 (2H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 3.40 (1H, br s, -OH), 4.63~4.67 (1H, m, ArCH), 5.08~5.14 (2H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 5.69~5.78 (1H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 7.22~7.30 (4H, m, ArH); **3g**, oil, ν_{\max} 3369, 3074, 2979, 1641 cm^{-1} , δ 2.34~2.44 (2H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 2.60~2.66 (1H, m, ArCH), 3.08 (1H, br s, -OH), 5.15~5.22 (2H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 5.83~5.89 (1H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 7.19~7.35 (3H, m, ArH), 7.56~7.58 (1H, m, ArH); **3h**, oil, ν_{\max} 3391, 3077, 2980, 1642 cm^{-1} , δ 2.44~2.52 (2H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 3.06 (1H, br s, -OH), 4.70~4.74 (1H, m, ArCH), 5.15~5.20 (2H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 5.74~5.83 (1H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$),

7.21~7.30 (3H, m, ArH), 7.37 (1H, s, ArH); **3i**, oil, ν_{\max} 3413, 3063, 2978, 1730 cm^{-1} , δ 2.38~2.50 (2H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 3.28 (1H, br s, -OH), 4.35~4.42 (1H, m, ArCH), 5.17~5.23 (2H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 5.81~5.95 (1H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 6.25 (1H, dd, J 15.9, 6.0 Hz, ArCH=CH), 6.63 (1H, d, J 15.9 Hz, ArCH=CH), 7.28~7.42 (5H, m, ArH).

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